

Design Optimization of Plastic Injection Mould for Additive Manufacturing

Prasad Mastakar, Imran Bijoli, Rushikesh Mhatre,
Chaitanya Sawant

Final Year Student, B.E.,
Department of Mechanical Engineering
MCT's Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Technology,
Mumbai, India

Amol Mangrulkar

Faculty and Research Scholar
Department of Mechanical Engineering
MCT's Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Technology,
Mumbai, India

Abstract : This research article aims to provide an overview of how an Additive Manufacturing (AM) mould can be optimized for its existing traditional design with advanced design techniques like topology optimization, generative design, lattice structure and conformal cooling channels which shows the potential of these techniques in AM as compared to other traditional manufacturing techniques. Key publications from the past two decades have been reviewed. This study concludes that the AM technique plays a dominant role in the manufacturing of mould with complicated structure which helps to improve the quality of final part and productivity. The outcome based on literature review and case study strongly suggested that in the near future, the AM method might become standard procedure in various manufacturing processes for fabrication of complex internal structure like conformal cooling channels and lattice structure in the mould. This article is beneficial to study the AM technique for development of the mould with conformal cooling channels and lattice structure and its applications in different AM manufacturing processes.

Index Terms- Additive Manufacturing, Generative Design, Topology Optimization, Conformal Cooling Channels, Injection Moulding.

I. INTRODUCTION

The onset of a globalized economy has given rise to a severely competitive business environment where in addition to cost, time is an important and game changing variable. While cutting edge technologies such as rapid prototyping have helped reduce development costs and timelines by an exponential margin, these technologies are not cost effective for mass production. Injection moulding is an important process for mass-market production of any component, and therefore, it was imperative to research and apply certain rapid prototyping and material science technologies to the injection moulding process in order to create a feasible solution that can be implemented for cost and time savings in the long run. Today's global market has brought a fundamental change in the product development philosophy where there are multiple manufacturers who produce the same product with different levels of quality. In a competitive environment, the manufacturer should be capable of developing a product in the least possible time without compromising on quality. This can be achieved with rapid prototyping method. Another aspect that needs to be considered is the manufacturing of moulds. Usually, these are machined from pre-cast blocks leading to a massive material wastage. This method of mould manufacturing does not allow for the implementation of conformal cooling channels. Rapid Prototyping enables us to manufacture moulds with zero material wastage. Additionally, due to the rapid advancements in Additive Manufacturing, it is easy to produce complex conformal cooling channels with techniques like 3D printing, Direct Metal Laser Sintering (DMLS), Selective Laser Melting (SLM).

This research article elaborates the design and analysis of a 3D printed mould for optimization used for plastic injection moulding. The aim of our project is to achieve significant reduction in lead time and overall production cost associated with injection moulding. Various design processes were researched and reviewed during the course of this project. A substantial reduction in the weight of cavity of the mould was achieved with the application of topology optimization technique. Our project also focuses on implementation of conformal cooling channels to achieve uniform cooling for quality improvement of products. We have achieved complete elimination of material wastage during machining of mould by using metal additive manufacturing.

II. AN OVERVIEW OF EXISTING MANUFACTURING PROCESSES AND RECENT TECHNOLOGIES

2.1 Injection Moulding

A low-cost alternative to rapid prototyping, injection moulding is a conventional plastic processing method to convert raw plastics to an object of practical use. Its success relies on the high capability to produce 3D shapes at higher rates than, for example, blow moulding. Injection moulding is the most widely used polymeric fabrication process. It evolved from metal die casting however unlike molten metals, polymer melts have a high viscosity and cannot simply be poured into a mould. Instead a large force must be used to inject the polymer into the hollow mould cavity. More melt must also be packed into the mould during solidification to avoid shrinkage in the mould.

Figure 2.1 Injection Moulding Process Flow

The injection moulding process is primarily a sequential operation that results in the transformation of plastic pellets into a moulded part. Identical parts are produced through a cyclic process involving the melting of a pellet or powder resin followed by the injection of the polymer melt into the hollow mould cavity under high pressure. One disadvantage with injection moulding is that the mould tends to be very expensive and modifications of the mould and the design of the part that are to be produced are common and cost-consuming. Computer-Aided Engineering (CAE) is an essential tool for simulation of the injection moulding process. Its proper use will minimize the amount of redesign and retooling. There are three main stages in the injection moulding cycle as shown in figure 1: Stage 1- Injection followed by Stage 2- Holding pressure and plasticating and finally Stage 3- Ejection of the moulded part. The main phases in an injection moulding process therefore involve filling, cooling and ejection. The cost-efficiency of the process is dependent on the time spent in the moulding cycle. Correspondingly, the cooling phase is the most significant step amongst the three, it determines the rate at which the parts are produced. As in most modern industries, time and costs are strongly linked. The longer is the time to produce parts the more are the costs. A reduction in the time spent on cooling the part before it is ejected would drastically increase the production rate, hence reduce costs. Conformal cooling channels are an excellent means of reducing the cooling time.

2.2 Rapid Prototyping

As with most manufacturing fields, production time and costs (lead and lag) are strongly correlated. The longer it takes to produce parts the more are the costs, and with injection moulding production industries cooling time is often taken as the indicator of cycle time. After new technologies are in place and moulding begins the cost is usually based on cycle time. Adjustments can be made to the moulding machine to help reduce the time to mould but in the final analysis the time is dictated by the ability of the mould to carry the heat away from the molten polymer. [2] At this stage, Rapid Prototyping (RP), comes into the picture as a viable supporting mechanism for the moulding process.

Figure 2.2.1 Additive Manufacturing steps

A number of rapid prototyping (RP) processes involve producing physical prototypes, layer by layer, directly from their CAD models without any human intervention. More appropriately, RP is known by the terms layered manufacturing (LM) and solid freeform fabrication (SFF). The principle of RP is illustrated in Fig. 2.1. The CAD model of the object is sliced by parallel planes. The edges of these slices thus obtained are squared. Thus, a complex 3D object is decomposed into several 2D objects or slices. These slices are physically realized in one of several ways, stacked and pasted together, to obtain the physical prototype. The accuracy of these prototypes, due to the staircase effect, can be improved by decreasing the slice thickness. For even better finish, polishing can be applied. Stereo-lithography (SLA), laminated object manufacturing (LOM), fused deposition modelling (FDM) and selective laser sintering (SLS) are some of the most popular RP processes, shown below in Fig 2.2.2

Fig 2.2.2 Three-Dimensional Printing Processes [3]

RP, introduced in 1989 as a design visualization tool has revolutionized the way products are designed and manufactured today. Although the prototypes could be made out of only soft materials, very soon, innovative methods of using them for making the short-run and production tools were developed using the existing technologies. Silicon rubber moulding, epoxy tooling, etc. are some of these indirect routes. Processes such as SLS can produce metallic and ceramic tools and hence are called direct rapid tooling processes. In these processes, the raw material is the required hard material coated with a soft binder. While selectively sintering during the layer building process, only the soft material melts binding the hard particles around it. The prototype thus obtained is initially in 'green state' that needs to be post-sintered and/or infiltrated

with a low melting material to get the desired mechanical properties for the tool. The properties of these tools will be invariably inferior to the conventional tools since the hard particles do not fuse together fully and the density is lower due to the presence of voids. [2]

2.3 Generative Design

The main objective of a generative design process is to implement CAD in the early stages of design to assist human designers to explore a larger range of design possibilities than what is manually possible [4]. Generative design in the domain of engineering provides powerful methods to automate design synthesis tasks, relieving the engineering designer from mostly routine tasks and generating a range of design alternatives within specific design domains. Further application areas include customized or even individually designed parts. From a set of requirements an existing product design can be improved as well as completely new designs generated [5].

Fig 2.3 Outline of Generative Design Process [4]

Autodesk describe four types of generative design tools that are emerging in field of DfAM (Design for Additive Manufacturing): form synthesis, lattice and surface optimization, topology optimization and trabecular structures. These methods may be regarded as design-by-search, or design-by-optimization. However, this mathematical approach often fails to incorporate human interaction and oversight throughout the design process. Recent research has tried to address this issue via human-computer interaction within generative design tools [6]. Although generative design methods are emerging as a popular approach for DfAM, they too are currently failing to couple design, representation, analysis, optimization and manufacturing techniques.

2.4 Topology Optimization

In topology optimization problems in real life, each finite element within the design domain is defined as a design variable, allowing a variation in density (homogenization, SIMP) or void-solid representation (BESO). Additional well-known topology optimization methods are: homogenization, ground structure, the level-set and the genetic method. Additive Manufacturing, a layer-wise material addition process family, may enable complex geometry and material distribution with increases in strength and stiffness, and, at the same time, reduced weight of the part. [7][8]

Fig 2.4 Various stages of topology optimization during analysis. [8]

Different reasons concerning fabrication time and cost minimization, including decentralized and on demand manufacturing, modifications and redesigns without penalties, possibility to make any complexity of geometry at no extra cost and time, increased supply chain proficiency as well as reduced environmental footprint are pointed out. Certainly, the materials should comply with the design and manufacturing techniques. Printing of long fiber composites is not achievable yet but functional parts can be printed directly with metal powders. Multi-scale structures (foam, 2D / 3D lattice) and multi-material design are also fostered by DfAM and can be used in combination with structural optimization. In addition, certain constraints are seen when implementing topology optimization in injection moulding – Primarily in the form of Rib Thickness Control and avoiding Interior Voids and Undercuts. For injection moulding/casting, part cooling and solidification are carried out with external devices such as cooling channels and air blowers. These devices speed up the cooling process but intensify the cooling imbalance, which causes residual thermal stress and distortion that negatively impacts the part quality, especially for the areas of varying rib thickness. Therefore, small rib thickness gradient or even constant rib thickness is required to relax the cooling imbalance. Another requirement is to avoid interior voids and undercuts, because these details can only be moulded by using extra devices such as movable mould inserts and will complicate the ejection process. In literature, there have been effective modifications of the optimization algorithm in satisfying this requirement, most notably by implementing modifications to the SIMP and Level Set Methods. [9]

2.5 Lattice Structure in Additive Manufacturing:

A lattice structure is an architecture formed by an array of spatial periodic unit cells with edges and faces. There are two- and three-dimensional lattice structures, and they are often linked to cellular solids. It is also known as lattice material because the micro architecture allows it to be viewed as a monolithic material with its own set of effective properties. Lattice structures have many superior properties, which make it a promising solution for various applications, such as a lightweight structure due to its high specific stiffness and strength, a heat exchanger due to its large surface area, an energy absorber due to its ability to undergo great deformation at a relatively low stress level, and an acoustic insulator due to its large number of internal pores.

A variety of conventional manufacturing techniques (e.g. investment casting, deformation forming and metal wire approaches) have been developed for fabricating lattice structures. However, these processes rely on complicated apparatus with precise process control and require further assembly or bonding steps to create the desired structures. In addition, the possible architectures are very limited when using these processes.

Fig 2.5 Example of lattice structures fabricated by different Additive Manufacturing processes: (a)FDM, (b) SLA, (c) SLS, (d) SLM, (e) EBM and (f) FEF [10]

The unique capabilities Additive Manufacturing technology possesses make it well suitable for manufacturing of parts with lattice structures. Various AM processes have been deployed for fabrication of lattice structures, and their manufacturability has been investigated. Some design methods for lattice structures have been proposed, and several specialized software programs have been developed to turn the conceptual technology into industrial practicality. [10]

2.6 Conformal Cooling:

Conventional, i.e. Parallel cooling channels are straight drilled channels in which the coolant flows from a supply manifold to a collection manifold. The collection manifold is designed with a larger diameter than the cavity's channels. Due to the flow characteristics of the parallel cooling channels, the flow rate along various cooling channels may be different, depending on the flow resistance of each individual cooling channel. The varying of the flow rate, cause the heat transfer efficiency of the cooling channels to vary from one to another. [11] As a result, cooling of the mould may not be uniform with a parallel cooling channel configuration, but a balanced parallel circuit provides uniform heat extraction.

Figure 2.6 Cooling Channels a) Conventional b) Conformal [12]

Conformal cooling designed for plastic injection moulding could be an attractive alternative to improve the plastic product quality, reducing cycle time and energy consumption. However due to the high costs to manufacture such cooling channels (additive manufactures techniques must be applied) together to the lack of knowledge about its quantitative benefits, this application is still incipient. [13]

III. DESIGN OF PART, MOULD AND COOLING CHANNELS

In order to validate the research conducted so far, a suitable component had to be selected in order to design a mould for it. A standard methodology commonly used for product and mould development was implemented for this. (Figure 3.2). It was essential that the component should be such that it can be manufactured using injection moulding, and have a uni-body structure. It was also necessary to ensure the said component had real-life applications, along with a three-dimensional design that would necessitate the need for conformal cooling channels to run through the mould cavity. Upon conducting a detailed secondary research, we noticed that battery and tool-box covers were fairly similar, as shown in Fig 3.1

Fig 3.2 Generalized Standard Methodology for development of Part and Mould using Rapid Manufacturing

Fig 3.1 Tool-Box Cover for Royal Enfield Bullet 350
(For illustrative purposes only)

This was followed by a series of discussion with our Industrial Guide, a veteran in the Auto-Ancillary industry, after which we decided to finalize “Motor-Cycle Tool-Box Cover” as the component for which the mould would be designed. After observing and studying designs offered by various automotive manufacturers, we decided to design a generic tool-box cover. This was done to ensure no design copyright violations would take place during the course of this research.

3.1 3-D Model of the Component:

A generic “Tool-Box Cover” having a rhomboidal shape was designed. The material for the tool-box cover is ABS Plastic, to facilitate manufacturing using Injection Moulding. A corresponding 3-D model of the Tool-Box Cover was designed using Autodesk Fusion 360 Software. This 3-D Model was further used as a source material during the designing of the mould.

Fig 3.3 3D Model of Component

3.2 Dimensions and Design of Mould:

A corresponding mould was designed to manufacture the component. The cavity of the mould was slightly heightened to accommodate the conformal cooling channels. In all, three iterations of the cavity were designed, one without cooling channels, one with regular cooling channels and one with conformal cooling channels. Details can be seen in Fig 3.4 showing the Plan, Elevation and Side Views of all iterations of the mould cavity.

Fig 3.4 Wireframe diagrams showing various iterations of the mould cavity

Using Siemens NX 12 software, 3-D Models of the components of the mould – its Core and Cavity – were prepared. For representational purposes, the 3-D Model of the cavity without any cooling channels is shown here

Fig 3.5 3-D Model of Core and Cavity of Mould

The material chosen for the core and cavity of the mould was Stainless Steel 316L. It was chosen due to its high tensile strength, a prerequisite for injection moulding but more importantly, it was an alloy that could be easily used as a material in an additive manufacturing process such as DMLS.

Material	Stainless Steel 316L
Young's Modulus	193000 MPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.25
Yield Strength	170 MPa
Ultimate Tensile Strength	485 MPa
Thermal Conductivity	0.0163W/mmC
Thermal Expansion Coefficient	1.59E-04/C
Specific Heat	500 J/kgC

Table 3.6 Material Properties

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To validate the design of the mould, stress-strain analysis was conducted on the mould designed for selected component using the simulation software ANSYS. Due to certain technical limitations, we were neither able to generate a 3D Model using Generative Design principles nor implement a Lattice Structure in the design of the Injection Moulding Mould. Applying an internal pressure of 138MPa, we have observed the following reactions in three different iterations of the cavity of the mould.

4.1 Stress-Strain Analysis of Cavity and Core

Fig 4.1.1 Stress Analysis of Cavity without Cooling Channels, showing distribution of load and deformation

Fig 4.1.2 Stress Analysis of Cavity with Regular Cooling Channels, showing distribution of load and deformation

Fig 4.1.2 Stress Analysis of Cavity with Conformal Cooling Channels, showing distribution of load and deformation.

The first set of analysis was conducted on a cavity from a conventional mould which did not have any provision for cooling channels. A maximum deformation of 0.06377mm was observed. The second set of analysis was conducted on a cavity from a mould which had conventional cooling channels bored in a straight line. A maximum deformation of 0.06677mm was observed. The third and final set of analysis was conducted on a cavity from a mould which had conformal cooling channels strategically lined along the contours. A maximum deformation of 0.06821mm was observed, marginally higher than the previous moulds.

4.2 Topology Optimization

After Stress-Strain analysis, a simulation using Topology Optimization was carried out using ANSYS. Figure 4.4 illustrates the visual details of this simulation. On performing Topology Optimization on the Cavity without Cooling Channels, we have reduced the original mass of 5.165kg to 1.587kg, which is a 69.28% reduction in mass. On the Cavity with Regular Cooling Channels, we have reduced the original mass of 7.596 kg to 3.786kg, which is a 50.16% reduction in mass. On performing Topology Optimization on the Cavity with Conformal Cooling Channels, we have reduced the original mass of 5.029kg to 3.016kg, which is a 40.03% reduction in mass.

Fig 4.2.1 Topology Optimization on Cavity without Cooling Channels

Fig 4.2.2 Topology Optimization on Cavity with Regular Cooling Channels

Fig 4.2.3 Topology Optimization on Cavity with Conformal Cooling Channels

The optimal design of conformal cooling is an emerging method and gives a better result as compared to the conventional channel. Fabrication of conformal channel can be done using various advanced techniques out of which additive manufacturing techniques are the emerging ones for complex part manufacturing. Implementation of topology optimization during analysis of the core and cavity of the component has resulted in approximately 45% reduction in weight thereby leading to lower production costs. Conformal cooling channels have been designed to ensure faster and efficient cooling of the component.

	Mould without cooling channels	Mould with Regular cooling channels	Mould with Conformal cooling channels
Pressure Applied	138 MPa	138 MPa	138 MPa
Min Stress	0.2707 MPa	0.2785 MPa	0.1944 MPa
Max Stress	15 MPa	15 MPa	15 MPa
Min Deformation	0 mm	0 mm	0 mm
Max Deformation	0.06377 mm	0.06637 mm	0.06821 mm
Original Weight	5.165 Kg	7.596 Kg	5.029 Kg
Reduced Weight	1.597 Kg	3.786 Kg	3.016 Kg
Percentage Reduction in Weight	69.17%	50.16%	40.03%
Percentage Reduction in Weight compared to Conventional Mould without Cooling Channels	0%	26.70%	41.60%

Table 4.2 Comparative Analysis of Result

V. CONCLUSION

The general consensus was that combining Topology Optimization, generative design along with conformal cooling channels has led to 41% reduction in weight of the mould, when compared with a conventional mould without any cooling channels which will also lower the cost and weight of the mould. In addition to providing a lower cost, due to the advantage of a reduced cooling time, the overall production performance of part by Injection Moulding along with the quality will be improved. The main conclusions can be summarized as follows:

1. CAE simulation and additive manufacturing techniques contribute to reducing the cycle time in the moulding processes by designing the cooling channels contoured to the shape of the core and cavity. These techniques help to increase the productivity and quality of the moulded parts.
2. For real-world application by implementing topology optimization and generative increases in strength and stiffness, and, at the same time, reduced weight of the part can be achieved through additive manufacturing.
3. Conventional manufacturing techniques (e.g. casting, forming and metal wire approaches) for fabricating lattice structures have multiple limitations and dependencies, therefore the possible architectures are very limited when using these traditional processes. This problem can be easily solved by using design for additive manufacturing, whose manufacturability for creating Lattice Structures has been investigated with positive results.
4. Complex-shaped CCC structures are studied by various researchers using simulation technique, but the manufacturing of such a complex shaped CCC is still the main hurdle even though a lot of advanced additive manufacturing techniques are available. The exact selection of CCC structure and additive manufacturing technique for particular manufacturing process (injection moulding, blow moulding, die casting, hot extrusion) for fabrication of desired part is not well established in previous literature, so further research is required to overcome this problem.

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